

Bias in Numbers Part 1: The Ontological Nature of 0, Real Numbers and ∞

By Allan Porter

What are Numbers Actually?

While the original purpose of numbers was simply as *iotas* to represent quantities and magnitudes, their use has been expanded over time to describe physical phenomena. Though systems built around these *iotas* have been undeniably successful in learning more about how the universe works, there still exists an inherent bias to using them in this way. For using magnitude and quantity as the basic tools of objective empiricism imply that they are the fundamental descriptors of everything in the universe. The truth however is that magnitude and size are merely measurements of components, but not of innateness. For they can only describe the “how many” of something but not the “what” of what that something is. This is why division by zero fails in contemporary mathematics. Division by zero implies the division of something into zero components. For it seeks mathematically the actual underlying nature of what the dividend really is at its core. Therefore, it doesn’t measure components and sizes, but what underlies them.

Division by 0

For example, if I started with 5 coins and then sought to divvy up those 5 coins into a single *pile*, then in terms of quantity I would have 1 *pile* of 5 coins ($5/1 = 5 \cdot 1$). If however, I wanted to divide those 5 coins into 0 *piles* what would the solution be? How many coins would I have per pile? Now maybe one can argue that I’d have 5 coins since if I divided a pile of 5 coins 0 times I’d get what I started with which would essentially be the same 1 pile of 5 coins. However, this would be wrong as division by 0 could not possibly merely indicate the absence of division since $5/1 = 5$ and $5/.5 = 10$. For as the divisor increases the solution should increase and not decrease. Therefore $5/0$ should equal a number far greater than 10 and not one less than 10. Furthermore, if essentially any tangible quantity of coins constitutes a *pile* and the divisor in division represents the number of *piles* one could have, then how could there ever be a case where there could be 0 piles of coins? For any quantity of coins would automatically constitute a pile simply by existing. Therefore, it would be impossible to have 5 coins contained in 0 piles since the mere presence of coins implies at least 1 pile by its very nature. Now maybe one could argue that actually splitting 5 coins into 0 piles would simply result in 0 coins then. The issues then is again that if $5/1 = 5$ and $5/.5 = 10$ then $5/0$ cannot be 0 since the solution should increase as the divisor does.

Therefore strictly speaking, any number divided by 0 would mathematically trend towards infinity simply because any number divided by an infinitesimally small number would have to trend towards an infinitely large number (If $1/.1 = 10$ and $1/.01 = 100$, then $1/0$ would need to be an infinitely large number). Because there is no means to actually reach zero from the perspective of the divisor (since if x keeps decreasing in $1/x$ then x would never actually equal 0 just an infinity small number), then $1/0$ would essentially yield a number that is infinitely large and never attainable (∞). Therefore at least arithmetically it can be said that $1/0$ would equal

∞ simply because division by 0 which is an infinitely small number would have to equal an infinitely large number.

How can $1/0 = \infty$?

However, rationally speaking how could $1/0 = \infty$? How could 1 coin split into 0 piles yield 0 pile of ∞ coins? This might work on a mathematical level but does it actually intuitively make sense? How could divide 1 into 0 groups ever get a number that is greater than 1 that was started with.

The answer is that there is a reason that every number (not just 1 but any positive number) divided by zero tends towards infinity. It is because what dividing 5 coins by 0 actually means is having to confront what the nature of coins really are beyond their components. While numbers in general such as 5 or 1 represent subjective quantities, objectively there are never just 5 or 1 coins in existence but always the highest amount of coins that there could possibly be - ∞ coins. Therefore what division by zero actually does is take a "subjective quantity" and then yield an "objective quantity". Furthermore, the "objective quantity" of any entity would then have to equal ∞ since there could never be less than an ∞ quantity of anything totally in existence. Therefore then dividing any quantity by 0 would have to equal ∞ . Now maybe one can argue - well there are only a finite number of coins in existence. Well, even if technically there are only a finite number of coins on Earth or in our physical universe, the statement is only true subjectively but not objectively. Since there are ∞ possible time periods and could be ∞ possible universes there would therefore also have to be ∞ possible coins in objective existence. For objective existence wouldn't only include the current time and universe as those would be merely subjective instantiations of "time" and "universe". Rather objective existence would constitute all times and universes. Therefore objectively, there would have to simply exist ∞ coins.

It is clear now how any quantity of coins split into 0 piles yields ∞ coins per pile. For piles themselves are subjective. What does a pile mean but a subjective instantiation of something that exists? If there are 5 coins per pile, then there are not actually 5 coins in existence but rather only 5 coins in existence from the subjective context that is that pile. Piles in general are therefore by their very nature subjective manifestations of objective quantity. For this reason, splitting a quantity of coins into 0 piles would essentially remove any subjective instantiation of objective quantity and return the number of coins in existence objectively - which would of course tend towards ∞ .

Arithmetic is not Objective

Using this logic, it is clear how arithmetic is essentially a subjective pursuit by its very nature. Numbers signify magnitude and quantity - the sizes and numbers of components of things. As in reality there are always an ∞ number of possible sizes and components for things that could theoretically exist then throughout all possible contexts there would need to always be only ∞ sizes and components of things. Objectively speaking, in the context that is all of existence, only the number ∞ makes any sense. Division by 0 is merely a method to get to that truth of objective existence from subjective quantities.

What is 0?

Now what about 0? Wouldn't the number 0 objectively exist? For objective reality would need to not only include the ∞ of all things that exist but also the 0 of all things that don't exist? It would have to include emptiness. Right?

Now while the concept of nothing can be used in terms of relative quantities and magnitudes, it does not actually exist anywhere in nature. For there can never be "nothing" of something since if there was nothing of something, the something would be without concept and impossible to fathom and therefore describe. For example, if 0 oranges objectively exist then there would never be any concept of "orange". Now maybe, one can argue that if there were "0 oranges" at some point in the future since at that time the fruit had become extinct, it could be said then that 0 oranges objectively exist. The problem with that would be that it wouldn't actually represent an objective 0 but rather a relative 0, since oranges will still exist then, just at a different time. Since time is a relative concept based on the subjective context of an observer, oranges would still objectively exist then, just not in the "context" that is that current time. To further explain, as time is relative, stating that there are 0 oranges in my pocket is the same as stating that there are 0 oranges in existence at the present time. Both cases merely represent a subjective 0 quantity of oranges relative to some other context. Whether that other context be at some other point in space outside of my pocket or at some other point in time, the fact still holds that there would only exist 0 oranges subjectively. For objectively even if 0 oranges exist at a certain point in time there would still be more than 0 oranges overall, since at some point in space or time there would have to have been 'oranges' at least as a concept which is what allowed them to take on a quantifiable existence in the first place.

Another example of this "non-existence" of objective 0 can be seen via *zero point energy* in quantum mechanics. To explain, the physical universe has been shown to never actually contain any "empty space" but rather be full of constant fluctuations of quantum fields where potential excitations in these fields constitute "virtual particles" that are constantly forming and dissipating. It is the fluctuation in these fields that are proposed to account for a degree of energy in every area of the universe. This has been demonstrated by detecting that there is actually energy between two conductive plates in a vacuum of empty space. This has been known as the 'Casimir Effect'. The charges of the plates are somehow affected by the quantum fluctuations of the empty space, indicating that the plates are interacting with these virtual particles even though they technically should not exist within a vacuum. Therefore, it can be seen that at least in terms of spacetime, there is no such thing as emptiness or "zero" actually existing.

However, since 0 is a concept shouldn't zero exist objectively? After all, can't it be argued that the mere idea of nothing alone proves its objective existence and therefore make nothing - something?

It can be said therefore that 0 really exists only when comparing the amount of "something subjective" relative to its state elsewhere. For if I have 0 oranges in my possessions, it does not imply that oranges don't objectively exist but simply that I don't have any oranges relative to the

oranges that exist elsewhere. 0 is thus merely a tool to describe a lack of relative subjective quantity. It therefore never describes “nothing” objectively but simply a lack of something from the perspective of a single context.

The term “0” is therefore misleading because the concept of “nothing” is manufactured and never observed. It is simply a *subjective number* and not something that exists in objectively reality. Even when imagining “nothing” there are many things that one could think of such as a single blank white space or an empty dark realm of spacetime. However, it is impossible to think of, picture or even fathom actual “nothing”. Why? Because nothing doesn’t exist.

Furthermore what are the similarities between these common mental schemas of nothing such as blank uniform spaces or just single planes of total darkness? The answer is simply the lack of separations in their representations. To further explain, blank uniform white spaces and planes of pure blackness do in fact constitute things that exist and not nothing. However, what is unique about them is their lack of separations, their lack of components, their lack of size. They are simply uniform entities with 0 components and 0 DIVISIONS within them. Therefore, what they really constitute is an objective whole. Intuitively, people know that when exiting the realm of “quantities” and “components” there only exists the innateness of things. However, due to the use of numbers and mathematics in describing physical phenomena, anything without size and components has been distorted to not only have 0 size and 0 components but rather also not exist. This is ultimately the fundamental flaw of mathematics - not accepting that its use is limited to describing subjective phenomena and the worlds of size and quantity. For zero would never mean nothing it would simply mean that which has zero size and components.

So What is Nothing then?

It can be seen from here that the reason the concept of “nothing” could exist without an objective existence of nothing is because the concept of “nothing” is not “nothing” but simply a placeholder term for that which is objective. For 0 describes something which has 0 size and 0 components not something that doesn’t exist. Only subjectively can 0 mean something that doesn’t exist since subjectively where there exist separations of magnitudes and quantities, there can simply be a lack of magnitude in quantity in one context relative to another context. However, objectively where there is no context but only 1 uniform whole of all contexts combined, there could never be any size or magnitude.

So therefore using this logic, what is objective 0? What has 0 size and 0 components? The answer would have to be something that has no separations within it and is in its most basic form. Therefore, while “nothing” objectively wouldn’t exist, zero still would objectively as something without separations within it. So what would this objective zero be?

What else is like this? What else can have no separations within it? The answer would be true ∞ . For Only the whole “block” of everything that exists is something which could not have a size or number of components. However, wouldn’t ∞ have to have all sizes and components within it which would essentially be the opposite of that with no size or components? How could this be the same as that without size/components?

The answer would be that “true infinity” would have no size or components because it is an objective entity that could not be compared to anything else. Since size and quantity are simply measures of things that exist in relation to one another, the whole of everything that exists can’t be measured in relation to anything else since it already includes the whole of everything that exists. For even if one were to compare “everything that exists” with “something that exists within it”, the “everything that exists” would no longer constitute ∞ , since it does not include the other “something that exists within it”. Therefore, ∞ can never have size or components since it can never exist subjectively. For if a context would ever contain true ∞ then it wouldn’t be a context anymore but have to be objective.

It can be seen in this way, that objective 0 is really just another word for ∞ . For generally what infinity really means is everything that exists. Therefore, infinity itself cannot actually have a size or measure of components objectively, since once infinity is split into a certain size or number of components it no longer constitutes infinity but rather a finite subset of infinity. Therefore, purely objectively ∞ like 0 simply means that without size.

If objectively 0 and ∞ are the same entity then would that mean the two are equal to one another? Wouldn’t everything without size and magnitude need to be the same thing?

Again this is an issue with using subjective quantities and sizes as a means of explaining “all of existence”. 0 Subjectively means a lack of quantity or size. However, objectively 0 does not exist and its objective terminology (the word “nothing”) is often confused with ∞ . Subjectively however, ∞ can never exist as ∞ automatically implies the existence of all contexts which could never be confined to just one context or else that context wouldn’t be a context but rather “every context”. Therefore subjectively, 0 is that which inside of one context has no size or quantity relative to another context. ∞ On the other is that which is the objective total of all contexts combined and therefore could never be confined to one context. They are therefore not the same thing since one is a purely subjective instantiation while the other is a purely objective instantiation.

The equation $1/0 = \infty$ is therefore disingenuous because it represents the collapse of a subjective context back into the objective realm. Therefore, while $1/0$ would yield ∞ it would not equal ∞ , since an equal sign implies the separation of context. Once ∞ is yielded, the equals sign dissolves and there is only ∞ . This is a concept that can’t be expressed in terms of arithmetic, since arithmetic implies the existence of two simultaneous contexts - one on the left hand side of the equals sign and the other on the right hand side. Any time ∞ exists however in one such equation it automatically collapses the entire equation outside the realm of context into the infinite whole since it would have to be inclusive of both signs of the equals sign. Sure, subjective ∞ can simply be regarded as an infinitely large number though this number would need to take on a discrete value if it was truly subjective and therefore not actually constitute all size or quantity in existence. For if it did it would cover not only one sign of the equals sign, but both sides and also all sides of all equal signs.

What is an equals sign anyway?

An equals sign is a separation between two contexts that seeks to make sense of how the 2 contexts compare objectively. What $1 = 1$ really means is not that 1 IS THE SAME THING as 1, but rather that a subjective instantiation of a single component has the same number of components as a SEPARATE subjective instantiation of one component. The two are not the same as they lie on two sides of the equals sign and therefore within 2 separate contexts. Now in order to join them in the same context, one must take the opposite of the right hand side (-1) and bring it over into the context of the left hand side 1. It is this that essentially dissolves the equal sign between the two contexts and joins them into one context. The only problem here is that once a separation between contexts is broken, the contexts themselves therefore must dissolve. This can be seen in $1 = 1$ which returns $1 + (-1) = 0$, which then returns $0 = 0$ essentially describing that the context has collapsed since one context with lack of quantity and another context with a lack of quantity would have to constitute no context at all since where there are no components there can be no context. Therefore, it could be said that $0 = 0$ returns ∞ since the two 0s dissolve back into the infinite summation of everything and all contexts. In this way equals signs are simply ways to dissolve contexts since every equals sign essentially ends with the following:

$X = X$ (two numbers are equivalent)

$X + (-X) = X - X$ (The right hand X is brought over to the left hand side as its opposite)

$0 = 0$ (A lack of context in both states dissolves the contexts)

∞

Note that if an equation contains no other components other than 0 then it is not a valid equation. The reason for this is that $0 = 0$ does not measure two separate contexts because the two contexts at that point are already emptied of components. Without components a context cannot exist so simply collapses back into the ∞ . For this reason, every equation essentially ends in a return to ∞ . What does this actually mean, how can any equation = ∞ ? The answer is that what an equals sign really is is a measurement. It is a measurement of one context against the other. It describes the entanglement of two contexts into one. It seeks to objectify contexts.

Once contexts are objectified they are no longer contexts but return to the objective state. Since ∞ describes what is objective then all equations would need to return ∞ . For once any measurement is made, ∞ is inevitable. Prior to measurement, yes two contexts can exist alone independent of one another with their respective components. However, once an equals sign is introduced, a measurement is made with the purpose of objectification. Therefore, the equation inevitably restores the state of ∞ .

So what does this tell us about ∞ ? If ∞ can never reside within in equation how can $1/0 = \infty$?

The answer is that it can but needs to be slightly modified. While $1/0$ RETURNS ∞ since the true innate nature of 1 divided up into 0 contexts returns the non-context whole ∞ . This ∞ instantaneously includes the $1/0$. Therefore $1/0 = \infty$ doesn't make sense since once the operations is valid ∞ can no longer equal $1/0$ since ∞ must only be on one side of the = sign and cant be confined to a context. Furthermore, since any equation must contain an equals sign

which separates contexts, an equation can never include ∞ since ∞ cannot be within a context, it cannot exist in two forms, it cannot be anything other than itself. Therefore $1/0$ returns ∞ but doesn't equal ∞ for if it did it would imply that $1/0$ is in a separate context from ∞ which means ∞ would be in a context and therefore not ∞ .

To summarize, I will explain the reasoning behind equations involving 0 and ∞ below. Remember that 0 is a subjective lack of components, while ∞ is simply every component in existence which by definition suggests that it cannot be confined to a context (since it contains all contexts simply by existing).

$x/0$ returns ∞ (since when x lacks context it must return to ∞)

$0/x$ returns 0 (since a lack of quantity confined to 1 component must still be a lack of quantity)

$x * 0$ returns 0 (since a lack of quantity any number of times is still a lack of quantity)

$\infty * x$ returns ∞ (since ∞ anything times must still be ∞)

∞ / x returns ∞ (since any time ∞ is in an equation it returns ∞)

∞ / ∞ returns ∞ (since any time ∞ is in an equation it returns ∞)

$\infty * \infty$ returns ∞ (since any time ∞ is in an equation it returns ∞)

Now that we have spoken about the nature of ∞ (all contexts which therefore also cannot be in a context itself) and 0 (a lack of quantity within a context) what can we say about all numbers in between?

Real Numbers

Real Numbers between 0 and ∞ are easy to describe. Since they only exist as a measure of components inside of a context they have no objective ontology, since objectively there would be no contexts at all and therefore a lack of components (only ∞ would exist). Thus, real numbers would simply only exist within contexts and not exist objectively.

What about One?

Yes it makes sense that all real numbers have subjective existences only as does 0, while ∞ has an objective existence only. However, what about 1? Even though 1 is a real number and describes a context shouldn't 1 also describe the amount of ∞ s there are $IE - 1$? For if there is one whole block of everything that is ∞ , doesn't that essentially equate to a component itself?

The answer is that thinking of ∞ as 1 is a bias of arithmetic. For in arithmetic where all of existence is said to be merely defined by components, it would make sense that everything in existence would also need to constitute a component itself and thus be 1 whole thing. However, the 1 in reality does not imply 1 thing but rather 1 component. Furthermore, 1 being a component also presupposes that it is part of a context. What is part of a context can by definition not define every context at the same time or else it wouldn't be a context. For example, since 1 is not 2 and 1 is not 3, it cannot constitute the whole ∞ since the whole ∞ must include separate context. The whole block of ∞ therefore is not one component but actually

every component and no component at the same time, for it exists in a world without components. Yes ∞ is technically a thing, but 1 is not a thing it is a component.

Summary

Therefore it can be said that ∞ defines that which is objective, the summation of all contexts without also being inside a context itself. 0 on the other hand represents a lack of components and therefore only exists relatively inside a context. However, once the 0 is in a context alone, the context collapses back into ∞ since it is without components. Real numbers between 0 and ∞ can like 0 only exist within a context since they constitute components which themselves cannot exist objectively since objectively there is only one infinite whole with 0 separation. It can be seen that there are essentially two types of numbers - objective numbers like ∞ and subjective numbers like 0 and all the real numbers. However does this really tell the real story? In the upcoming sections, I will focus on negative numbers, irrational numbers, complex numbers and also super-numbers.